

THE ROLE OF MODERN YOUTH IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: Youth is the future of any society. In a literal sense, they are the greatest wealth and priceless treasure of Uzbekistan. After all, the youth of new Uzbekistan is the basis of our future and prospects.

Key words: spirituality, people, personality, upbringing, tolerance, freedom.

Аннотация: Молодежь – это будущее любого общества. В буквальном смысле они являются величайшим богатством и бесценным сокровищем Узбекистана. Ведь молодежь нового Узбекистана – основа нашего будущего и перспектив.

Ключевые слова: духовность, народ, личность, воспитание, толерантность, свобода.

Youth is the future of any society. In a literal sense, they are the greatest wealth and priceless treasure of Uzbekistan. After all, the youth of new Uzbekistan is the basis of our future and prospects. Today in our country all the forces and opportunities are used for their perfect mastering of modern science and high technologies, in particular, it makes a lot of sense that presidential and creative schools are being created.

Now we can rightly be proud of the achievements of young people studying in educational buildings equipped according to modern requirements and with all conditions. In our opinion, supporting the construction of sports, music and art schools for children through the rapid development of public-private partnerships and private services in the field, especially in the field of advanced education in English, computer science, mathematics and other subjects in demand, will use the huge potential of the private sector which will definitely pay off in a short time.

If we look at the history of the developed countries of the world, we will see that reforms aimed at changing the life of society began with the education system. The system has been radically reformed in Uzbekistan as well. Many changes have been made in this field for the benefit of young people, state policy in the education system has been improved.

School is the basis of education and training. In this regard, the quality of education in schools should be high both in the capital and in remote villages. It is known that in recent years, 98 specialized schools have been established in order to provide deep education to young people. The creation of Presidential schools in each region also serves to educate talented and competent youth. In addition, higher education coverage of young people has been increased. In 2016, there were 65 higher education institutions operating in our country, and in 2021, the total number of higher education institutions in the republic has more than doubled to 127. To date, 130 types of activities of universities have been created in the republic:

- state higher education institutions - 96;
- non-state higher educational institutions - 9;
- foreign OTMs and their branches - 25.

This list does not include military and religious higher education institutions, including organizations that have established a master's degree.

Necessary conditions are being created for young people to acquire knowledge.

But, we must remember that the basis for the development of the modern generation is proper education. Here language and literature become indispensable assistants. As the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi wrote, “a book is a grateful teacher, the most important source of knowledge and spiritual growth”. There are many proverbs about the importance of reading books in the language of our people, getting a decent education, mastering a profession. An important factor that has been showing people the right path for thousands of years, making them educated, professional and, of course, happy, is to be friends with books. In educational institutions, this process helps to increase the level of knowledge of students and strengthen their intelligence.

That is why our main task is to educate young people who are versatile, comprehensively thinking, intellectually mature, able to meaningfully analyze any information.

Enlightenment is always aimed at raising the consciousness, education and culture of people. The concept of enlightenment is connected with the concepts of culture and spirituality. It saves people from ignorance and evil deeds, helps to have good manners and habits. Enlightened a society of educated people will always prosper and improve. Enlightened, educated youth is the future of New Uzbekistan!

In a word, over the past five years, the ground has been created for the comprehensive support of young people, so that they grow up as perfect people. This emphasis on youth is finally paying off. The achievements of our youth at the international and national levels are a vivid confirmation of this. There is no doubt that as a result of these reforms, our future will be in the hands of such young people. Because today's youth is the basis of our tomorrow, New Uzbekistan, the Third Revival.

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